

IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION OF ORGANIZATIONAL STRESS RESOURCES FOR BANK STAFF

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***Abstract:** In general, the order caused by factors that disturb the stress disorder is defined as the response of the individual body. It is therefore seen as a negative situation. However, a sufficient level of stress in individuals' personal development and to contribute to the solution of the problems mentioned issues. This is the positive side of stress. When we look at the organizational aspects of the situation fails to meet the expectations of the job and working conditions of organizational stress arises. On the other hand, the motivation of employees in terms of achieving targets related to individual and organizational goals are important. Individuals also if they can motivate themselves to a certain extent, increase the motivation of employees in the organization also it has an important contribution and responsibility. Here's the low or high motivation that has significance in terms of organizational stress. In this regard, it is useful to know that only what the effect on work motivation level of organizational stress. This study analyzed the effect in question in terms of bank employees. In addition, both organizational stress, as well as the presentation of the elements necessary to know whether that measure work motivation to show significant differences by demographic variables, studies have examined these issues.*

***Key Words:** Bank Employee, Stress, Organizational Stress, Job Satisfaction*

Today, organizations are paying very large fees to cope with stress. People on both organizational and see if they experience serious damage as a result of individual stress. There fore the organization, they biliçlen about organizational stress, and take the necessary measures to keep stress under control and the optimum level of stress has become a necessity. It constitutes an important part of people's daily life, business or profession. Business is also the only

person in the world has an important function in terms of not economically and psychologically. Job satisfaction of employees is related to their own thoughts about how they see their work and business. Organizations that require them to give importance to many reasons for job satisfaction is concerned. factors that adversely affect employees' job satisfaction of managers are required to be conscious and sensitive about. It is also known to have a negative impact on job satisfaction of

employees of organizational stress. by research carried out in the bank's employees work in this direction; The relationship between job satisfaction and organizational sources of stress are analyzed.

1.1. The concept of organizational stress

The success or failure of the organization is no doubt that employees are directly related to the success or fail. The success of the employees of the organization will lead to success. The satisfaction of employee, is one of the goals of the organization. Another aim of the organization is to ensure satisfaction in itself. In other words, it is not active. The organization of individual satisfaction and operable to provide organizational efficiency and to meet the needs of the organization and must take place in a balanced manner from both sides of the object. However, it is currently defined as the concept of quality customer satisfaction. organizations to achieve this satisfaction; to act responsibly towards their customers, so they can understand customers' needs and expectations and are required to meet these expectations and requirements. External factors to satisfy customers, so that internal customers are not satisfied with the condition of the employees for the success of the organization. Job satisfaction of employees is related to their own thoughts about how they see their work and business.

2. Research Methodology

There is a survey of banks in the banking sector carried out on the branch

employees. In this section, the demographics of the bank employees, employees are given to the relationship between stress levels and job satisfaction and job satisfaction levels and demographic characteristics and included review on the relationship between organizational stress levels.

Performance by measuring the productivity of employees in organizations (success) and the first studies to examine the concept of performance evaluation in a systematic and formal, in the early 1900s through Taylor's work measurement application is being made in organizations as scientific. There is a nearly 80-year history of the studies on performance evaluation in Turkey and this work is done in the public sector is seen as the first (and us is that Gümüştekin Oztem, 2005, 280).

2.1. The sampling and Boundaries of Research

Rather theoretical and general or specific sample is fed from the funds of the practical work, mainly research literature literature and constitute the limits of the sample of the research.

2.2. Collection and Analysis of Datas

The literature on the subject is made. Theoretical framework has been prepared. for researchThe effect of bank staff job satisfaction of organizational stress sourcesIt will be set forth in the theory and practice of performing evaluation studies.

3. Results

The research was conducted with the participation of 60 employees of the bank. Research is formed from three sections. Age related to demographics Personal Information Form in the first chapter, gender, educational background, work experience, work time, position, every demographic feature in the answers given to questions like choosing my status, select willingly work was assessed as a percentage and in itself. Of those surveyed in the evaluation of the data collected, • More than half of (54.0%) consists of women, • More than half of (56.7%) were between 21 and 30 years of age, • the majority (83.2%) were university graduates, • Nearly half (48.7%) were administrative denomination has no employees • more than half of (57.7%) are 4 years and over time that people who do the banking profession, • the majority (81.5%) that they voluntarily chose their profession, • Nearly half of (47.3%) from 1 to 3 years already emerged in the bank they work they work. Developed by Aydin in order to determine the stress levels of employees in Research Resources Organizational Stress Scale were used. Aydin (2004; 341) in the study of physical conditions in the business environment is considered as sources of organizational stress, physical conditions in the business environment in some of the other studies on this subject are discussed as environmental factors. 3 questions was developed by the researchers to assess their individual stress factors in this section. In this case the scale comprises five sub-dimensions. The last dimension when analyzing organi-

zational stress factor 4 is designed to evaluate the size of the individual stress factors. Organizational stress factors, stress due to organizational policy, organizational structure resulting from stress, stress related to the nature of the work, are grouped as stress from interpersonal relationships. In the third part of the study is to measure the satisfaction levels of employees Eroglu (2004; 143) by Minessot Job Satisfaction Scale was used which improved job satisfaction scale basis. job satisfaction due to job satisfaction and work content originating from around the scale comprises two dimensions including job. The results of the factor analysis, the scale of the Erogluer (2004) as detecting the study confirm that consists of two dimensions. work with data collected on demographic characteristics of the sample in the study satisfaction, the relationship between stress levels. The relationship between stress levels and job satisfaction were examined. dimensions of organizational stress levels of employees in the study were found to be as similar to each other and mediocre level. However, employees have emerged relatively stress because they live up to the organizational structure. Relatively employees' stress levels have emerged about the nature of the work is at the lowest level. On the other hand, employees were found to be mediocre level of individual stress levels. However, the stress level of individual bank employees participated in the survey, which is significantly lower than the level of organizational stress. Stress from interpersonal relationships in the supply of

banking experience in organizational stress, stress caused by organizational policy, and individual stress has emerged as a significant effect on stress caused by organizational structure. The resulting stress levels of employees arising from organizational policy which is less than 1 year based on the results of banking experience, is lower than the longer employees with banking experience. insufficient wages and salaries imbalance of stress resulting from organizational politics, authority and incompatibility of responsibility, displacement of frequent business, the lack of task-related responsibilities, do both of the jobs contradictory, performance evaluation and promotion injustice and banking experience factors such as excessive disciplined working environment We can say that much, which creates more stress on people. banking experience less of a negative effect on a person's banking experience is stress from interpersonal relations than those with more. Banking experience of workers with less than 1 year, the problems in the superior-subordinate relationship, overly competitive situation, the factors that create stress arising from relationships between people, such as the lack of conflict and support by longer working with banking experience possible to say that less affected. Again banking experience 1 employees the same job with less stress on the lower level of the year they live according to the individual who is 4 years and older. Made banking experience in research 1 year less, than it is between 4-7 years of experience in banking appeared to be a negative effect on the stress caused by

organizational structure. Still working people in the bank as working time in the case where less than 1 year, 4-7 years experience stress is stress resulting from lower individual and organizational policy by working in the same bank. If the position of the bank employees revealed that they have a significant effect on the stress arising from the structure of the business. According to employees at the lower levels of employees in managerial positions at higher levels of mid-level executive positions with respect to the structure of the business it can say they experience stress. of employees who are in the middle-level managerial positions in the bank, time pressure, working hours in an uncertain situation, the monotony of work, excessive workload, we can say customers menuniyetsizlig and complained of fear and that they were more affected by factors such as excessive bureaucracy and was under more stress due to these reasons. When the job satisfaction of employees who participated in the study were examined around the employee should work in terms of content and business were found to be inadequate level of job satisfaction. Relatively satisfied employees are more prized than the content of the work around the business. When the job satisfaction of employees caused by the business environment it looks at the relationship between demographic characteristics; satisfaction levels of employees they need around the business of banking experience, selection position and the banking profession willingly except in cases where no significant difference was

seen compared to other demographics. According to the banking experience of people between the results obtained not less than 1 year 4-7 years of banking experience, arising around 1-3 years 8 years and job satisfaction and work according to the above is effective on the negative. At this point in the banking industry for 8 years and older with experience of employees according to the person with 4-7 years experience more job satisfaction heard of, they have a positive opinion of these employees if they meet the requirements related to the business environment, organizations they work can be a result of more confusion. The gender of employees according to the research results obtained, age, education level and seniority could tell no difference between the effects in terms of job satisfaction and situations arising around their business. As previously it highlighted the work, like the work that the business is foremost factors of job satisfaction. Using the capabilities of the employee's job is suitable, innovations in learning, be possible to develop, employee creativity, change and take responsibility, routing the employee based on solving a problem that is necessary features to satisfy the liking of business and business (Basaran, 2000; 218). Society was not adopted by enough to imagine that individuals and business life while preparing himself to work in the study of job satisfaction decreases. According to the results of this study also voluntarily have chosen the profession of banking employees, business and business environment arising from the content of the

work according to those who voluntarily choose a higher level of satisfaction. Also studies were found to be related to the position of the periphery of the work due to job satisfaction. of those in senior management positions in Research, work caused by working at other positions around the job satisfaction is clear that a higher level. In this case, the employees' quality of life could be explained by factors that increase a person with rising levels of job satisfaction. The management team is working in that instill the idea that how important the work that that person, compared to non-administrators to ensure that more job satisfaction. Relations between job satisfaction and demographic characteristics resulting from the job content is seen that a significant effect on job satisfaction resulting from the nature of the termination of the work is examined. 1 is currently running less than a year to work in a bank, according to the seniority of the facilities promoted between 1 and 3 years of work, working conditions, to see if the money's done a good job, more job satisfaction than they were able to obtain useful work for the company because it is the feeling of accomplishment to get up and running. At the same time that people in senior management positions, according to employees arising from the job content in the mid-level and lower-level management positions and other positions have a positive effect on job satisfaction it is. Senior managers in both the working position and from the content of the job of job satisfaction levels resulting from the periphery of the

work will be higher than that in the lower position its employees in the organization. intermediate and lower level executive positions resulting from business content and business by employees at other positions and have a positive effect on satisfaction. Senior managers in both the working position and from the content of the job of job satisfaction levels resulting from the periphery of the work will be higher than that in the lower position its employees in the organization. intermediate and lower level executive positions resulting from business content and business by employees at other positions and have a positive effect on satisfaction. Senior managers in both the working position and from the content of the job of job satisfaction levels resulting from the periphery of the work will be higher than that in the lower position its employees in the organization.

Conclusions and recommendations

A large part of the day people are spending their working places. It is negatively affect many sources of stress in the work environment of staff, so no need to prepare the groundwork for the formation of the workplace as well as at home many unwanted situations. In particular, stress in the workplace employees from both spiritually and physically to get sick and may cause the efficiency of the work as a result. In this study, a study was made on issues related to the stress of working in the vegetable oil factory. As a result of studies; employees' ages increased, reduced the effects of stress caused by the transmitter itself in the form of

interpretation, the increasing age of the worker to decrease the effects of stressful arising from the structure, education with high levels of self from the stressful arising from the interpretation in the form of education level are affected much more than those with low levels of education with a high rating from stressful due to the nature of the work, education level more affected than those with low, highly educated workers, physical environment reflected stressful for they are more sensitive and it found they were affected in a negative way. In addition, employees of man or by the fact that women on the gender of the stressful no significant difference between stressful that have the same effect, the staff's wife works or stress ERDOGAN with not working - UNS is - MILK 460 2009 is not a significant difference between the makers, social workers, who is married they experience more stress than single-makers in terms of stress, According to those who use social stressful for employees and stressful arising form self-reviews smokers it was found to have more stress. Finally, the SS among white-collar workers with work blue-collar workers surveyed, KY, OS, and that there is no difference in terms of FC, of stressful of the two groups of influence in the same direction and stressful working life has been shown to cause similar effects on both groups. Businesses who work in stressful resources managers and employees should be aware of the diagnosis should be good. Thus, they can protect themselves both employees should take measures in advance and they will do with the application.

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